

CORENEXT

White Paper

Trustworthiness

The Key to Europe's Digital Future

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COREnext Releases White Paper: Trustworthiness – The Key to Europe's Digital Future

Press Release

May 2024

COREnext, a EU-funded project focused on advancing Europe's digital infrastructure, released its latest white paper, "Trustworthiness – The Key to Europe's Digital Future." This comprehensive study examines the critical role of trust and security in the digitalisation process, underscoring the essential steps needed to maintain Europe's leadership in high-end consumer goods.

The COREnext white paper will be presented during [Convened Session 4](#) at the EUCNC | 6G Summit in Antwerp, Belgium, on Wednesday, 5 June 2024, at 16:00 by Fredrik Tillman from Ericsson and Zulaicha Parastuty from Infineon. The whole session will be devoted to the importance of trustworthiness in the digitalisation process.

The paper opens with a discussion, based on Abraham Maslow's theory, on the significance of trustworthiness for both humans and machines in a fully connected world. It acknowledges digitalization as both a challenge and an opportunity for Europe, stressing the necessity to focus on areas and technologies that enable a secure digital future.

Key recommendations outlined in the white paper include:

- Ensuring the reliability and security of processing units.
- Exploring scalable and flexible digital infrastructures.
- Advancing sensing technologies and physical layer innovations.
- Developing secure and reliable Radio Access Networks (RAN).

A call to action is extended to stakeholders to embrace these priorities, emphasising the importance of trust and security. This will ensure a continued high European value content in products as these become a natural and integrated part of consumers' digital ecosystems.

To know more about the white paper, please visit the [COREnext website](#).

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